

Callus production and plant regeneration efficiency in *Oryza* species, Tamil Nadu, India.

Species and cultivar	Seeds inoculated (no.)	Seeds (no.) with callus	Callus production ^a (%)	Calli inoculated (no.)	Regenerating calli (no.)	Regeneration efficiency ^b (%)
<i>O. spontanea</i>	68	26	38.2	42	12	28.5
<i>O. glaberrima</i>	73	40	54.5	42	9	21.4
<i>O. sativa</i>						
Cultivar Co 43	62	15	24.6	24	2	4.5
Cultivar IR50	68	42	61.7	44	18	40.9
Cultivar IR1552	72	39	54.2	36	7	19.4

^aCallus production (%) = $\frac{\text{no. of seeds with callus}}{\text{no. of seeds inoculated}} \times 100$. ^bRegeneration (%) = $\frac{\text{no. of regeneration calli}}{\text{no. of calli inoculated}} \times 100$.

regeneration frequencies are given in the table.

The banding patterns of esterase isozymes could be utilized as markers in in vitro studies by correlating banding patterns with frequencies of callus induction and regeneration. □

The International Rice Research Newsletter is published to expedite communication among scientists concerned with rice research and the development of improved technology for rice and rice-based farming systems. Readers are encouraged to write authors at their published addresses to discuss the research and obtain more details.

Disease resistance

Reaction of selected cultivars to tungro (RTV) and other diseases in Tamil Nadu

V. Mariappan, V. Narasimhan, M. Muthusamy, S. Muthusamy, and P. Vivekanandan, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Madurai 625104, India; and G. S. Khush, IRRI

All locally grown cultivars were severely damaged by RTV in 1984. We screened

newly selected breeding lines for resistance to RTV using the vector green leafhoppers for artificial inoculation at 10 d. Lines showing 0-10% infection were compared with popular local varieties ADT36, CO 37 (Vaigai), White Ponni, and IR20 in the field.

Six lines (IR32429-148-1-3-3, IR35366-90-3-2-1-2[IR72], IR37865-29-3-1-3, IR39357-91-3-2-3, TNAU831520, and TNAU831521) were least infected with leaf blast (0-2 grade), neck blast (1.6 to 12.8%), and brown spot (1-3 grade) and showed sheath rot moderate infection (3-5 grade). The four popular local varieties showed high RTV

infection with artificial inoculation but moderate resistance to other diseases in the field. The yield potential of the six cultures was comparable with that of the local varieties, or even better (see table). □

A conceptual model of disease resistance in rice pathosystems, and its implications for evaluating resistance

S. W. Ahn and M. F. Koch, IRRI

We developed a conceptual model to focus understanding of quantitative resistance, defined as the ability of a host population to limit disease intensity. Quantitative resistance in rice usually consists of two components: the efficiency of qualitative resistance to eliminate the avirulent portion of the available inoculum and partial resistance to lower disease infection caused by virulent isolates (Fig. 1).

Partial resistance is best measured by challenging a population of rice plants with selected virulent isolate(s) alone, avoiding exogenous inoculum (alloinfection). A variety with

Yield and reaction to diseases of rice lines in Tamil Nadu, India.

Line or variety	Plants infected with RTV ^a (%)	Leaf blast ^b (grade)	Neck blast ^b (%)	Sheath rot ^b (grade)	Brown spot ^b (grade)	Mean yield (t/ha)
IR32429-148-1-3-3	0.0	2	3.3	3	3	5.7
IR35366-90-3-2-1-2 (IR72)	0.0	0	2.0	3	1	6.8
IR37865-29-3-1-3	10.0	0	12.8	5	2	5.1
IR39357-91-3-2-3	10.0	2	7.8	3	3	6.1
TNAU831520	6.3	0	1.4	5	3	5.9
TNAU831521	5.9	0	1.6	5	3	6.4
Local checks						
ADT36	70.0	0	19.4	5	3	5.1
CO 37	50.0	0	20.0	5	2	5.5
White Ponni	20.0	3	—	3	3	4.9
IR20	66.7	3	12.5	5	2	5.2

^aArtificial inoculation. ^bField infection under natural conditions.